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Highlights

- Two new formulations for the Probabilistic Pickup-and-Delivery Travelling Salesman Problem
- The need of approaching the probabilistic case is discussed
- An efficient branch-and-cut algorithm based on the non-compact formulation is proposed
- None of the formulations clearly dominates the other

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The Probabilistic Pickup-and-Delivery Travelling Salesman Problem

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Abstract

Transportation problems are essential in commercial logistics and have been widely studied in the literature during the last decades. Many of them consist in designing routes for vehicles to move commodities between locations. This article approaches a pickup-and-delivery single-vehicle routing problem where there is susceptibility to uncertainty in customer requests. **The probability distributions of the requests are assumed to be known**, and the objective is to design an a priori route with minimum expected length. The problem has already been approached in the literature, but through a heuristic method. This article proposes the first exact approach to the problem. Two mathematical formulations are proposed: one is a compact model (i.e. defined by a polynomial number of variables and constraints); the other one contains an exponential number of inequalities and is solved within a branch-and-cut framework. Computational results show the upsides as well as the breakdowns of both formulations.

Keywords: travelling salesman, pickup-and-delivery, probabilistic TSP

1 Introduction

Transportation of goods and people is a fundamental concern of modern societies. The adequate design of routes for vehicles is crucial in any transportation system.

This paper deals with the problem of finding a route for a single vehicle under uncertainty in customer requests. The vehicle routing literature has addressed several problems governed by this uncertainty. A seminal problem in this area is the so-called *Probabilistic Travelling Salesman Problem* (PTSP). In this problem a set of locations is given, each of which is associated with a given probability of requiring a service. The PTSP looks for a sequence of all the locations, called *a priori route*, before the realization of the random process. After the realization of the random process, the locations with a formalized request must be visited once by the vehicle following the *a priori route*, while the locations with no request should not be visited. Therefore, the vehicle may operate a non-Hamiltonian route called *a posteriori route*. The aim of the PTSP is to determine the *a priori route* such that the expected cost of the *a posteriori route* is minimum. The PTSP was introduced by Jaillet (1988) and later addressed by, e.g., Laporte et al. (1994); Liu (2007); Marinakis and Marinaki (2010, 2016); Miranda and Conceicao (2016); see HENCHIRI et al. (2014) for a survey.

[This work](#) addresses a more complex problem called the *Probabilistic Pickup-and-Delivery Travelling Salesman Problem* (PPDTSP). It is an extension of the PTSP where the route must start and finish at the depot and the other locations are grouped in pickup-delivery pairs. Each potential request may be formalized, or not, according to a Bernoulli probability distribution, so that if a certain request is not formalized, the vehicle must skip visiting the pair of locations associated to it.

The assumption that the probability of requiring service is the same for all customers limits the applicability of [this](#) approach. Still, similar assumptions exist in the literature. For instance, in the context of facility disruption probabilities, many articles have considered the problem of planning appropriated locations when all the facilities have the same disruption probability; see e.g. Shen et al. (2011); Snyder (2006); Snyder and Daskin (2005) among others. On the other hand, the PPDTSP is quite challenging even under this assumption and [the results obtained on this problem](#) could be a good starting point for future research considering the case of different probability distributions. Furthermore, as it will be discussed in the next section, to the best of the authors' knowledge, this paper is the first in the literature proposing an exact approach for the PPDTSP.

The remainder of the article is structured as follows. Section 2 reviews the literature related to the PPDTSP, which is later described with detail in Section 3. Section 4 discusses the necessity of specific models for the PPDTSP, since optimal solutions for the deterministic version of the problem, equivalent to the extreme scenario where all the requests are formalized, may be far from being optimal solutions for the PPDTSP. Section 5 shows two mathematical formulations: one is a compact model; the other formulation has an exponential number of inequalities and is solved within a branch-and-cut algorithm. Section 6 analyzes computational experiments showing that the non-compact model is able to solve larger instances with up to 31 locations. Finally, Section 7 concludes with some final remarks and suggestions for future work.

2 Literature review

The PPDTSP was introduced by Beraldi et al. (2005), that approached the problem heuristically. The authors assumed that all probability distributions are independent. Another assumption, also considered in the PTSP, is that the re-optimization of the route is forbidden once the a priori route has been computed. Only the minor change of skipping an unformalized visit to a location is allowed, and the a posteriori route must follow the order fixed by the a priori route. These two assumptions conform the so-called *static policy* and are made in the present work as well. The static policy is quite common in vehicle routing problems with stochastic data (see e.g. Louveaux and Salazar-González (2018)). See e.g. Pillac et al. (2013) for other planning strategies defining other related vehicle routing problems. Beraldi et al. (2010) extends the results in Beraldi et al. (2005) to the multi-vehicle PPDTSP, while Ho and Haugland (2011) proposes local search heuristics for the multi-vehicle variant along with time windows and capacitated vehicles, known as the *Probabilistic Dial-a-ride problem*. The PPDTSP can be seen as the problem of moving several commodities, each one from one source to one destination; see e.g. Louveaux and Salazar-González (2009) for a problem transporting one commodity between locations with stochastic demands.

It is worth noting that the PTSP becomes the well-known *Travelling Salesman Problem* (TSP) when the probability of requiring a service is 1 for each location. In the same way, the PPDTSP is also another studied deterministic problem when each request has probability 1 to be formalized. This problem is called *Pickup-and-Delivery Travelling Salesman Problem* (PDTSP), and it has been studied by several authors in the literature (see, e.g., Dumitrescu et al. (2010)). In addition, exact approaches for several extensions of the PDTSP are also studied in the literature. Among others, Gouveia and Pesneau (2006), Ascheuer et al. (1990) and Balas et al. (1995) studied a generalization of the PDTSP where each location may be the origin or destination of several requests, known as the *Precedence-Constrained Asymmetric Travelling Salesman Problem* and also as the *Sequential Ordering Problem*; Cordeau and Laporte (2007) studied the multi-vehicle variant with time windows, known as the *Dial-a-ride problem*; Hernández-Pérez and Salazar-González (2009) and Letchford and Salazar-González (2016) studied the capacitated variant of the PDTSP, known as the *Multi-commodity one-to-one Pickup-and-Delivery Travelling Salesman Problem*.

Even though there are several articles dealing with problems related to the PPDTSP, to the best of our knowledge, it does not exist any literature regarding exact approaches to solve the PPDTSP. This is the major contribution of the current paper.

3 Problem Description

As mentioned earlier, the PPDTSP is an extension of the PTSP where one location (called *depot*) is the starting and ending location of the route, and the customer locations are grouped in pairs. Each pair of locations represents a potential request to transport a product from the first location (pickup) to the second location (delivery). Each potential request may be formalized, or not, according to an independent Bernoulli probability distribution. Re-optimization of the route is not allowed once the a priori route has been calculated: only skipping unformalized visits is permitted, and the route that is actually performed must always follow the itinerary given by the a priori route on the formalized visits. If a potential request is formalized, its pickup location must precede its delivery location along the route. Otherwise, the vehicle must skip visiting the pair of locations associated to that request. There is no vehicle capacity or time constraint to be considered.

As a result, a feasible solution for the PPDTSP is an a priori route that allows all requests to be served, i.e., visiting all locations and satisfying all the precedence relationships. As for the PTSP, the realization of the random variables will be known after the a priori route has been decided, and the vehicle will visit only the locations of the formalized requests following the sequence in the a priori route. Travel costs between locations are given in advance, and therefore each route is associated with a *cost* defined as the sum of the travel costs between consecutive locations along the route. Note that, while the cost of an a priori route is a deterministic value, the cost of the a posteriori route is a random variable at the time of deciding the a priori route. An optimal PPDTSP route is an a priori route whose a posteriori route has a minimum expected cost.

To help the reader, the usual notation introduced in previous articles on pickup-and-delivery problems is used in this work, as summarized here. The number of potential requests is denoted by n . Each request is represented by a pair of nodes $(i, i + n)$ in a graph, with i representing the origin of the request and $i + n$ the destination. The set of all origins is denoted by P . The set of all destinations is denoted by D . Node 0 represents the depot where the vehicle starts and ends its route. Thus, the node set V of the graph is $\{0\} \cup P \cup D$. The arc set A contains the pairs of nodes representing direct trips that the vehicle could perform along a route. For example, $(0, i)$, $(i + n, 0)$ and $(i, i + n)$ are in A , but $(0, i + n)$, $(i, 0)$ and $(i + n, i)$ are not. Each arc $a \in A$ is associated with a travel cost c_a . For any node i , let $\bar{c}(i)$ denote the node that corresponds to the same request than i (also known as the *companion node*), that is, $\bar{c}(i) = i + n$ if $i \in P$, and $\bar{c}(i) = i - n$ if $i \in D$. Finally, $V \setminus S$ is denoted as S^c .

4 Need for solving the probabilistic case

This section is intended to show that an optimal solution for the (deterministic) PDTSP, although feasible for the PPDTSP, may have an expected cost far from optimal.

Let p be the probability of a request being formalized. Figure 1 shows (in blue) three routes for an instance with 5 requests. The pickup nodes are located on a circumference (in green) of radius 5 centered at the origin. The delivery nodes are located on a circumference (in red) of radius 30. The depot is the center of both circumferences. The nodes of each type are evenly distributed on each circumference. The travel costs between nodes different from the depot are proportional to the corresponding Euclidean distances, and all travel costs from or to the depot are zero. The leftmost route in the figure is the optimal PDTSP route (i.e., $p = 1$), while the central and rightmost routes are optimal PPDTSP routes for $p = 0.3$ and $p = 0.05$, respectively. The routes depicted in Figure 1 do not show the trips from or to the depot, whose travel costs are zero, in order to avoid any possible confusion with the travel costs between customers, that are Euclidean distances. Furthermore, the depot is not depicted either, because with zero travel costs to and from it, its *geographical* representation would actually be irrelevant.

Figure 1: Optimal PPDTSP routes

The cost of the optimal route for the PDTSP is 184.7, and the costs of the optimal PPDTSP routes when $p = 0.3$ and $p = 0.05$ are 218.3 and 223.6, respectively. The expected cost of the a posteriori route associated to the optimal PDTSP route is 56.29 when $p = 0.3$ and 7.21 when $p = 0.05$, while the expected costs of the a posteriori route associated to the optimal PPDTSP routes with $p = 0.3$ and $p = 0.05$ are 54.8 and 7.0, respectively. Not surprisingly, the costs of the a priori solutions when $p < 1$ are higher than the optimal PDTSP costs, and the expected costs when $p < 1$ are lower than the expected costs of the optimal PDTSP. This example confirms that the probabilistic problem may have optimal routes which are different from the optimal routes of the deterministic problem.

Furthermore, the differences between the optimal PDTSP route and the optimal

Figure 2: Costs of optimal PPDTSP tours for different p (horizontal axis) and different radii for the circumference with deliveries (colored lines).

PPDTSP routes increase with the radius of the larger circumference containing the delivery nodes. Figure 2 shows the costs of the a priori PPDTSP tours for different probability values (p , horizontal axis) and when the delivery nodes are on circumferences of increasing radii. There is one line for each radius in $\{5 + 2.5t : t = 0, 1, \dots, 10\}$. When the radius is smaller than 15, the optimal PDTSP route is also an optimal PPDTSP route for any value of p . However, when the radius is greater than or equal to 15, the optimal PPDTSP routes vary with the value of p , and the differences with the optimal PDTSP routes increase as p decreases.

As far as the authors are concerned, general bounds for the magnitude of the difference between the expected value of an optimal PDTSP tour and the expected value of an optimal PPDTSP tour for each p are not known. However, they can be calculated for some particular cases. In order to illustrate this, let us consider a particular case in which the cost matrix has only four different values: the costs of all arcs from and to the depot are 0; a is the cost from i to $i+n$ and from i to t for all $i, t \in P$; b is the cost from $i+n$ to $t+n$ for all $i, t \in P$; and c is the cost of any other arc. If $a < b < c$, and $(n-1)b < (n-2)c + a$, the route

$$0 \rightarrow 1 \rightarrow 2 \rightarrow 3 \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow n \rightarrow 1+n \rightarrow 2+n \rightarrow 3+n \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow n+n \rightarrow 0 \quad (1)$$

is an optimal PDTSP route with cost $v^*(PDTSP) = (n-1)a + (n-1)b + c$. However, this is not an optimal PPDTSP route, since the expected cost of this route is greater than the expected cost of the route

$$0 \rightarrow 1 \rightarrow 1+n \rightarrow 2 \rightarrow 2+n \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow n \rightarrow n+n \rightarrow 0, \quad (2)$$

which is $ap + (n-1)c$. Jaillet (1988) proved that the expected cost of an a priori route in the PTSP can be computed as the sum, for all the arcs, of the arc cost

multiplied by the probability of that arc to be traversed in the a posteriori route. This result was extended in Beraldi et al. (2005) to the PPDTSP. Note that, if $i, j \neq 0$ correspond to different requests and there are exactly r requests between i and j in the a priori route, then the probability of arc (i, j) to be in the a posteriori tour is $p^2(1-p)^r$; that is, the probability that requests i and j have to be served and the r requests visited in between are cancelled. If $j = i + n$ or one of them is the depot, then the probability of arc (i, j) is $p(1-p)^r$.

Hence, if the a priori route is (1), then the arcs in the a posteriori route are of six types:

- arcs in (1), all of them with probability p^2 ,
- arcs of type $(i, i + 1 + t)$ for $i \in P \setminus \{n, n - 1\}$, $t \in \{1, \dots, n - 1 - i\}$ with probability $p^2(1-p)^t$ (the cost of all these arcs is a),
- arcs of type $(i, i + n)$ for $i \in P$ with probability $p(1-p)^{n-1}$ (the cost of all these arcs is a),
- arcs of type $(i, i + 1 + t)$ for $i \in P \setminus \{1, n\}$, $t \in \{n - i, \dots, n - 2\}$ with probability $p^2(1-p)^t$ (the cost of all these arcs is c),
- arcs of type $(n, n + 1 + t)$ for $t \in \{1, \dots, n - 2\}$ with probability $p^2(1-p)^t$ (the cost of all these arcs is c),
- arcs of type $(i + n, i + 1 + t + n)$ for $i \in P \setminus \{n, n - 1\}$, $t \in \{1, \dots, n - 1 - i\}$ with probability $p^2(1-p)^t$ (the cost of all these arcs is b).

Weighting the costs of all the arcs in the a posteriori route by its probabilities, it holds that the expected cost of route (1) is

$$v_1 = p^2 \left((n-1)a + (n-1)b + c \right) + \sum_{t=1}^{n-2} (n-1-t)ap^2(1-p)^t + nap(1-p)^{n-1} + \sum_{t=1}^{n-2} tcp^2(1-p)^t + \sum_{t=1}^{n-2} cp^2(1-p)^t + \sum_{t=1}^{n-2} (n-1-t)bp^2(1-p)^t.$$

On the other hand, if the a priori route is (2), then the only arcs that may appear in the a posteriori route are the arcs in (2), those whose cost is a with probability p and those whose cost is c with probability p^2 , and the arcs $(i + n, i + 1 + t)$ for all $i \in P \setminus \{n, n - 1\}$ and $t \in \{1, \dots, n - 1 - i\}$, those whose cost is c with probability $p^2(1-p)^t$. Thus, the expected cost of route (2) is

$$v_2 = nap + (n-1)cp^2 + \sum_{t=1}^{n-2} (n-1-t)cp^2(1-p)^t.$$

Denoting $q = 1 - p$ and using the formula for the sum of m terms of a geometric series with first term α and common ratio $\beta < 1$,

$$\sum_{k=1}^m \alpha \beta^{k-1} = \frac{\alpha(1 - \beta^m)}{1 - \beta},$$

it follows that

$$\begin{aligned} v_1 &= p^2 \left((n-1)a + (n-1)b + c \right) + bp \left((n-1)q - q^{n-1} - \frac{(q - q^{n-1})}{p} \right) + napq^{n-1} + \\ &ap \left((n-1)q - q^{n-1} - \frac{(q - q^{n-1})}{p} \right) + cp(q - q^{n-1}) + c(q - q^{n-1}) - (n-2)cpq^{n-1}, \\ v_2 &= nap + (n-1)cp^2 + cp \left((n-1)q - q^{n-1} - \frac{(q - q^{n-1})}{p} \right) \end{aligned}$$

and thus v_1 might be greater than v_2 , which is larger than or equal to the optimal PPDTSP cost. The magnitude of the difference $v_1 - v_2$ depends on a, b, c, n and p . For instance, for $n = 5$, $p = 0.1$, $a = 1$, $b = 100000$ and $c = 1333333$, it holds that $(v_1 - v_2)/v_2 = 0.65$, so the optimal PDTSP route has an expected cost at least 65% greater than the optimal PPDTSP route.

Even though optimal PDTSP routes are naive heuristic solutions for the PPDTSP, from the analysis in this section it follows that they may be far from being optimal for the PPDTSP. In the following section two different formulations for the PPDTSP are introduced, allowing to solve the PPDTSP to optimality.

5 Mathematical models

This section presents two alternative formulations for the PPDTSP. One is a compact formulation, while the other one contains an exponential number of constraints. Both formulations are based on the following set of binary variables. For $i, j \in V$ and $r = 0, \dots, n-1$, let x_{ij}^r take value 1 if and only if

- the vehicle goes from i to j visiting other locations between them involving exactly r requests, and
- neither of the locations visited between i and j are $c(i)$, if $i \neq 0$, nor $c(j)$, if $j \neq 0$ (the companion nodes of i and j).

Note that variables x_{ij}^0 describe the a priori route. For brevity, $x^r(S : T)$ is used instead of $\sum_{(i,j) \in A: i \in S, j \in T} x_{ij}^r$ for any subset of nodes S and T . In addition, $R = \{0, \dots, n-1\}$.

Hence, the objective function of the PPDTSP is

$$\min \sum_{r \in R} \left(\sum_{i \in P} c_{0i} x_{0i}^r p (1-p)^r + \sum_{i \in D} c_{i0} x_{i0}^r p (1-p)^r + \sum_{i, j \in P \cup D: j \neq i+n} c_{ij} x_{ij}^r p^2 (1-p)^r + \sum_{i \in P \cup D} c_{i, i+n} x_{i, i+n}^r p (1-p)^r \right). \quad (3)$$

The first and second terms correspond to the first and last arcs in the a posteriori route, respectively. The third and fourth terms correspond to arcs in the route connecting locations associated with different and the same requests, respectively.

5.1 Compact formulation

To model the PPDTSP with a polynomial number of constraints, let us also consider the binary variables used in Sarin et al. (2005) for the asymmetric travelling salesman problem (ATSP). For $i, j \in V$, let w_{ij} be 1 when i precedes j in the route, and 0 otherwise. Then the a priori route described by the x_{ij}^0 variables must satisfy the following constraints.

Each location must be visited once:

$$x^0(V : i) = 1 \quad \text{for all } i \in V \quad (4)$$

$$x^0(i : V) = 1 \quad \text{for all } i \in V \quad (5)$$

The w variables must represent a precedence:

$$w_{ij} + w_{ji} = 1 \quad \text{for all } i, j \in P \cup D \quad (6)$$

$$w_{ij} + w_{jk} + w_{ki} \leq 2 \quad \text{for all } i, j, k \in P \cup D \quad (7)$$

Each request imposes a precedence constraint on the corresponding companion nodes:

$$w_{0,i} = w_{i, i+n} = 1 \quad \text{for all } i \in P \quad (8)$$

The precedence must be coherent with the x variables:

$$\sum_{r \in R} x_{ij}^r \leq w_{ij} \quad \text{for all } i, j \in P \cup D \quad (9)$$

Note that $\sum_{r \in R} x_{ij}^r$ is 1 if and only if i precedes j in the a priori route and there is

no location in between related to the request of i and j . Therefore,

$$\sum_{r \in R} x_{0i}^r = \sum_{r \in R} x_{i,i+n}^r = 1 \quad \text{for all } i \in P \quad (10)$$

$$\sum_{r \in R} x_{i0}^r = \sum_{r \in R} x_{i+n,i}^r = 0 \quad \text{for all } i \in P \quad (11)$$

$$\sum_{r \in R} x_{i0}^r = \sum_{r \in R} x_{i-n,i}^r = 1 \quad \text{for all } i \in D \quad (12)$$

$$\sum_{r \in R} x_{0i}^r = \sum_{r \in R} x_{i,i-n}^r = 0 \quad \text{for all } i \in D \quad (13)$$

Also

$$\sum_{r \in R} x_{ij}^r = w_{ij} \quad \text{for all } i \in D, j \in P \quad (14)$$

$$\sum_{r \in R} x_{ij}^r \geq w_{ij} + w_{j,i+n} - 1 \quad \text{for all } i, j \in P \quad (15)$$

$$\sum_{r \in R} x_{ij}^r \geq w_{ij} - w_{i,j-n} \quad \text{for all } i, j \in D \quad (16)$$

$$\sum_{r \in R} x_{ij}^r \geq w_{j-n,i} + w_{ij} + w_{j,i+n} - 2 \quad \text{for all } i \in P, j \in D \quad (17)$$

and

$$x^{r+1}(i : V) \leq x^r(i : V) \leq 1 \quad \text{for all } i \in P \cup D, r \in R \quad (18)$$

$$w_{jk} + \sum_{s=r}^{n-1} x_{ij}^s + \sum_{s=0}^{r-1} x_{ik}^s \leq 2 \quad \text{for all } i, j, k \neq 0, r \quad (19)$$

$$\sum_{s=r}^{n-1} x_{ij}^s + \sum_{s=0}^{r-1} x_{i0}^s \leq 1 \quad \text{for all } i, j, r \quad (20)$$

$$\sum_{s=r}^{n-1} x_{ij}^s + \sum_{s=0}^{r-1} x_{0j}^s \leq 1 \quad \text{for all } i, j, r \quad (21)$$

Finally,

$$x_{ij}^r \in \{0, 1\} \quad \text{for all } i, j, r \quad (22)$$

$$w_{ij} \geq 0 \quad \text{for all } i, j. \quad (23)$$

The linear-programming (LP) relaxation of this formulation can be strengthened by adding valid inequalities for the Precedence-Constrained Asymmetric Traveling Salesman Problem (PCATSP).

5.2 Non-compact formulation

An alternative formulation can be written by using the x_a^r variables only. The cost of not having additional variables is to have an exponential number of constraints instead. However, as it will be proved later, the constraints can be managed through efficient approaches, and the lower bounds obtained by solving the LP relaxation of the non-compact formulation are usually higher (and thus better) than the ones from the compact formulation.

5.2.1 The mathematical model

The new formulation includes the same objective function (3), the degree equations (4)–(5), and the integrality constraints (22) for $r = 0$.

To force x^0 representing a pickup-and-delivery tour, note that PPD TSP solutions are also feasible solutions of the PCATSP. As a result, valid inequalities for the PCATSP are also valid for the PPD TSP, as mentioned before. Balas et al. (1995) introduces:

$$x^0(S \setminus \pi(S) : S^c \setminus \pi(S)) \geq 1 \quad (24)$$

$$x^0(S^c \setminus \sigma(S) : S \setminus \sigma(S)) \geq 1 \quad (25)$$

for all $S \subseteq V \setminus \{0\}$, where $\pi(S) = \{i \in P : i + n \in S\}$ are the predecessors of S , $\sigma(S) = \{i \in D : i - n \in S\}$ are the successors of S , and $S^c = V \setminus S$. These inequalities can be considered as strengthening the subtour elimination constraints for the ATSP.

This section concludes with other inequalities to force x_{ij}^r , with $r > 0$ to have the right values. For any $i, j \in V$ with $i \neq j$ and all $S \subseteq V \setminus \{0, i, j, c(i), c(j)\}$ with $|\{s \in P : s \in S \text{ or } s + n \in S\}| = r$, the following constraint is valid.

$$x^0(S : S^c) \geq x^0(i : S) + x^0(S : j) - x_{ij}^r. \quad (26)$$

Note that $x^0(i : S) \leq 1$, $x^0(S : j) \leq 1$, and $x^0(S : S^c) \geq 1$, so constraint (26) is obviously satisfied if at least one of these inequalities hold strictly (i.e., not with equality). If $x^0(i : S) = 1$, $x^0(S : j) = 1$, and $x^0(S : S^c) = 1$, then the a priori tour contains a path that enters S from i , visits consecutively all nodes in S , and leaves S to j . Given that S contains nodes of r requests, x_{ij}^r must be 1, and this is exactly what (26) forces. Note that, when x_{ij}^r is not forced to be 1 by constraints (26) then the variable will go to 0 due to the positive coefficient in the objective function (3). Note also that this implies that the use of constraints (26) means that variables x_{ij}^r , for $r > 0$ will take integer values in the optimal solution provided that variables x_{ij}^0 are integer. Thus, in this formulation, integrality constraints (22) are used only for $r = 0$. Constraints (26) are called *skip-constraints* and they are similar to the *precedence forcing constraints* introduced by Ascheuer et al. (1990) for the Sequential Ordering Problem.

5.2.2 Additional constraints

Some additional constraints are used in order to strengthen the formulation and thus improve the value of the lower bound obtained when the integrality constraints are relaxed.

In particular, the so called *simple* (π, σ) *inequalities* introduced by Balas et al. (1995) are used for the PCATSP. These inequalities can also be written as:

$$x^0(S : S^c) \geq x^0(S : 0) + 1 \quad (27)$$

for all $S \subseteq V \setminus \{0\}$ such that there exists $i \in S$ and $i + n \notin S$. Constraints (27) mean that, if a set S contains a pickup node whose corresponding delivery node is not in S , then a path that visits consecutively all the nodes in S and immediately goes to the depot is not feasible.

Other valid inequalities for the PPDTSP formulation, not coming from the PCATSP, are

$$\sum_{r \in R} (x_{ij}^r + x_{ji}^r) \leq 1 \quad \text{for all } i, j \in V \setminus \{0\}, i \neq j. \quad (28)$$

5.2.3 The branch-and-cut algorithm

The non-compact formulation described above has an exponential number of constraints, which are managed through a branch-and-cut algorithm that can be outlined as follows:

Step 0. Let $BestLB = 0$ be the current lower bound and $UB = +\infty$ the current upper bound.

Step 1. Define a relaxed problem with the objective function (3), the degree equations (4)–(5), equations (10)–(13), constraints (28), and $0 \leq x_{ij}^r \leq 1$ for all $i, j \in V$ and $r = 0, \dots, n-1$. Initialize a list \mathcal{L} with this problem.

Step 2. If \mathcal{L} is empty or $BestLB = UB$, then STOP. Otherwise, extract a problem from \mathcal{L} .

Step 3. Solve the current problem. Let OBJ be the solution value. If $OBJ < UB$, update $BestLB$; otherwise, go back to Step 2.

Step 4. Identify inequalities (24)–(27) that are violated by the current LP solution by using adequate separation procedures. (If the solution is integer, use the special separation procedures described in Section 5.2.4.)

Step 5. If some violated inequalities have been identified, add these inequalities to the problem and go back to Step 3. Otherwise, if the current solution is integer and feasible, set $UB = OBJ$, and go back to Step 2.

Step 6. If the current solution is not integer, generate two subproblems by branching on a fractional variable. Insert the subproblems into \mathcal{L} and go back to Step 2.

Cutting planes are introduced in Steps 4 and 5 in order to improve the current bound at each node and to incorporate the constraints from those sets with an exponential cardinality. The update of *BestLB* (lowest lower bound of all the non-fathomed nodes) is done as usual in a branch-and-bound algorithm. Finally, the strong branching strategy implemented in IBM-ILOG CPLEX 12.6 is used to explore the branch-and-cut tree.

The next section describes several separation procedures that have been designed to identify violated inequalities (24)–(27).

5.2.4 Separation algorithms

Let \bar{x}^0 denote the current LP solution. Given that some of the relaxed inequalities are needed to guarantee the feasibility of the integer solutions, **it has to be assured that** those inequalities are satisfied by those solutions. On the other hand, identifying inequalities violated by integer solutions is usually much easier than by fractional solutions. Thus, **the procedures designed for separating invalid integer solutions are presented first.**

Separation algorithms on integer solutions

When the current LP solution is integer, finding a violated inequality (24)–(26) (if any) can be done in polynomial time. If for any $i \in P$, the location $n + i$ is visited by the path before the location i , simply define S as the set of nodes from $i + n$ to i in the path (excluding i) to find a violated constraint (24). Violated constraints (25) can be found in a similar way.

For checking the violation of constraints (26), a simple procedure consists of enumerating all pairs (i, j) such that i is visited before j . Let S be the set of nodes visited between i and j along the path. Then, if $c(i)$ or $c(j)$ are in S , (26) is not valid and a different pair must be considered; otherwise, let r be the number of requests involved in S , and check the violation of the inequality defined by i, j, S, r .

These procedures are applied every time that the current optimal LP solution is integer. If all these procedures fail to find violated inequalities, then the current integer solution is feasible.

Min-cut Separation algorithm for (26)

Taking into account that an exact procedure to solve this separation problem in polynomial time is not available, we propose a heuristic approach that has produced good results in our experiments. This approach is based on rewriting (26) as

$$x^0(S : S^c) + x^0(i : S^c) - x^0(S : j) - x_{ij}^0 \geq 1 - x_{ij}^r - x_{ij}^0,$$

which is equivalent to

$$x^0(S \cup i : S^c) - x^0(S \cup i : j) \geq 1 - x_{ij}^r - x_{ij}^0. \quad (29)$$

Note that the set S cannot contain any of the nodes in $\{0, i, j, c(i), c(j)\}$ and r is the number of different requests associated with the locations in S . The separation algorithm consists in finding a set S minimizing the left-hand side of (29) (which can be done by solving a max-flow problem on an appropriated network) and then checking the potential violation of (26) by \bar{x} , where r is the number of commodities involved in S . This algorithm is of a heuristic nature because, if the inequality is not violated, there is no guarantee that a different S with a different r could define a violated inequality instead.

It only remains to describe how to build the network for fixed i and j , and a given (fractional) solution \bar{x} . To this end, consider a dummy node s and the graph G' with node set $V' = V \cup \{s\}$ and arc set $A' = A \cup \{(s, i) : i \in V\}$. Let us denote $W = \{0, i, c(i), c(j)\}$. Associate each arc $a \in A'$ with a capacity given by 2 if $a \in (W : j)$, by 0 if $a \in \delta^-(j) \setminus \{(i, j)\}$, by \bar{x}_a^0 if $a \in A \setminus \delta^-(j)$, and by $\bar{x}_{(i,v)}^0$ if $a = (s, v)$ for any $v \in V \setminus \{i\}$. Then the solution of the max-flow problem with source s and destination j divides V into two sets, and the capacity of the associated cut is the left-hand side of (29).

Separation algorithms for (24)–(27)

Although (24) and (25) have been used by several authors in relation with the PCATSP, we are not aware of any exact algorithm for separating them. Balas et al. (1995) describes an exact approach for weaker inequalities that are obtained when $\pi(S)$ in (24) is replaced by $\pi(j)$, where $j \in D \cap S$, and $\sigma(S)$ in (25) is replaced by $\sigma(j)$, where $j \in S \cap P$. The procedure for weak (24) consists in computing, for each $j \in D$, the maximum flow between j and the depot 0 in a graph with node set $V \setminus \{j - n\}$ and capacities of the arcs \bar{x}_{ij}^0 . Similarly, the procedure for weak (25) computes the maximum flow between 0 and each $j \in P$ in the graph with the same capacities and node set $V \setminus \{j + n\}$. If any of these maximum flows is less than 1, a violated inequality exists for the set S associated with the corresponding min-cut (see Balas et al. (1995) for additional details). Obviously, the stronger inequalities (24) and (25) are checked and added if they are found to be violated. Inequalities (27) can also be separated by computing the maximum flow from every $j \in P$ to $j + n$ in the graph with the same capacities and where node 0 has been removed. In what follows, several heuristic procedures that have also been used to separate (24)–(27) are described.

Consider the undirected graph $G_u[\bar{x}^0]$ where each pair of arcs (i, j) and (j, i) is replaced by an edge $e = \{i, j\}$ with weight $\bar{x}_e^0 = \bar{x}_{ij}^0 + \bar{x}_{ji}^0$. Most of the heuristic procedures presented in this paper consist in generating promising sets of nodes that are used to check the violation of constraints (24)–(27). Roughly speaking, the promising sets S are those for which $\bar{x}^0(S : S^c)$ is as small as possible. Given a set of

nodes S , checking the violation of constraints (24), (25), and (27) is straightforward. Constraints (26) are checked by first finding the nodes i and j that maximize $\bar{x}^0(i : S)$ and $\bar{x}^0(S : j)$, respectively.

First, the node sets of the *connected components* of $G_u[\bar{x}^0]$ and $G_u[\bar{x}^0] \setminus \{0\}$ are generated. Other promising sets are generated by using the so called *shrinking* procedure. This procedure iteratively shrinks any edge of $G_u[\bar{x}^0]$ with weight 1, where shrinking an edge $\{i, j\}$ means replacing nodes i and j by a new super-node, say v_{ij} , that is linked to any node u that was adjacent to i or j by an edge $\{v_{ij}, u\}$ with weight $\bar{x}_{iu}^0 + \bar{x}_{ju}^0$. Every time a new super-node is created, the corresponding subset of original nodes is used to check the violation of the constraints.

The *growing sets* procedure is used to generate more *promising* subsets. This procedure starts with an initial subset $S = \{i\}$ for each $i \in V \setminus \{0\}$, and iteratively adds to it a new node $j \notin S \cup \{0\}$ such that $\bar{x}^0(S : j) > 0$ is as large as possible, until no more nodes can be added. For each subset of nodes $S \subset V \setminus \{0\}$ generated by this procedure, the possible violations of the corresponding constraints (24)–(27) are checked.

The separation algorithms for fractional solutions are executed as follows. First, the *connected components* of $G_u[\bar{x}^0]$ are computed, and then the *shrinking* procedure is run. If the number of violated constraints found by these procedures is less than $2n/3$, the *growing sets* procedure is called. If the number of violated constraints found so far is still less than $2n/3$, the min-cut algorithms that separate inequalities (24), (25), and (27) are executed. Finally, if the number of violated constraints found so far is less than $2n/5$ then the min-cut separation algorithm for (26) is run.

6 Computational results

Computer codes to solve the two formulations were implemented by using the MILP solver IBM-ILOG CPLEX 12.6 on a personal computer with Intel(R) Core(TM) i7-4790 CPU with 3.6 GHz, 32 GB of RAM and Microsoft Windows 10 64bits. A time limit of 2 hours was imposed on each execution. The two codes have been tested on PPDTSP instances built from the PDTSP instances in Dumitrescu et al. (2010) called `probnX` with $n = 5, 10, 15$ and $X = a, b, c, d, e$. The number of locations on these instances goes up to 31. Five PPDTSP instances have been obtained from each original PDTSP instance by using $p \in \{1.0, 0.9, 0.8, 0.2, 0.1\}$. Note that $p = 1$ corresponds to the deterministic PDTSP case, $p = 0.8, 0.9$ correspond to a reliable network, and $p = 0.1, 0.2$ correspond to an unreliable network. Since the instances with $p = 1$ are easier to solve and give good upper bounds for the instances with $p < 1$, the expected cost of the solution found for each instance with $p = 1$ is given as initial upper bound when solving the corresponding instance with $p < 1$. In order to do this, the instances with $p = 1$ are solved first, followed by the instances with

$p < 1$. To ensure that the solver will generate the optimal solution when ending before the time limit, this initial upper bound is rounded up to the nearest integer number.

The results are organized in ten tables, whose main characteristics are given in Table 1.

Tables 2–6 show the results **obtained** when solving the compact formulation. The column headings have the following meaning:

BestLB: lower bound when the execution ends.

BestUB: upper bound when the execution ends.

Gap: value $100 \times (BestUB - BestLB) / BestUB$.

B&B: total number of branch-and-bound nodes (apart from the root node),

Time: computing time, in seconds, when the execution ends. *T.L.* indicates that the time limit of 2 hours is reached and thus the code finishes without optimality proof. The time values corresponding to the fastest of the two tested formulations are highlighted in bold.

LB0: lower bound from the LP relaxation at the root node.

Rows *avg*, highlighted in italics, give the averages.

Tables 7–11 show the results **obtained** when solving the non-compact formulation. These tables also show the following columns:

Lpt: time consumed by the MILP solver.

Sept: time consumed by the separation procedures.

cuts: number of generated inequalities found by the separation procedures.

(24): number of generated inequalities (24).

(25): number of generated inequalities (25).

(26): number of generated inequalities (26).

(27): number of generated inequalities (27).

cut0: number of generated inequalities at the root node.

A conclusion from the results in Tables 2–6 is that the compact formulation can only solve the smallest instances, with 5 requests, with the exception of `prob10e`

Formulation	$p = 1$	$p = 0.9$	$p = 0.8$	$p = 0.2$	$p = 0.1$
compact	Table 2	Table 3	Table 4	Table 5	Table 6
non-compact	Table 7	Table 8	Table 9	Table 10	Table 11

Table 1: Classification of result tables

Instance	BestLB	BestUB	Gap	B&B	Time	LB0
prob5a	3585.0	3585.0	0.0	71	2.4	3414.2
prob5b	2565.0	2565.0	0.0	0	0.3	2524.3
prob5c	3787.0	3787.0	0.0	72	1.9	3496.0
prob5d	3128.0	3128.0	0.0	1	0.2	3068.6
prob5e	3123.0	3123.0	0.0	73	2.2	2772.3
avg	-	-	0.0	43.4	1.4	-
prob10a	4389.2	5141.0	14.6	1159	T.L.	4076.6
prob10b	3950.6	5300.0	25.5	1632	T.L.	3619.7
prob10c	3804.8	4096.0	7.1	947	T.L.	3336.3
prob10d	4197.0	4575.0	8.3	773	T.L.	4132.8
prob10e	4874.0	4874.0	0.0	871	3486.3	4575.4
avg	-	-	11.1	1076.4	6457.6	-
prob15a	4470.7	-	-	0	T.L.	4470.7
prob15b	4030.0	-	-	0	T.L.	4030.0
prob15c	4695.6	-	-	0	T.L.	4695.6
prob15d	4665.8	-	-	0	T.L.	4665.8
prob15e	4543.8	-	-	0	T.L.	4543.8
avg	-	-	-	0.0	T.L.	-

Table 2: Compact formulation on instances with $p = 1$

and $p = 1$. The code did not finish solving the first LP relaxation on the instances with 15 requests and $p = 1$, and even a feasible integer solution was not found. The main reason is the large number of constraints in the compact formulation, all given to the MILP solver in advance.

From Tables 7–11 it can be concluded that the non-compact formulation performs better when p is large. It is faster in the instances with 5 requests. It solved all instances with 10 requests when $p = 1$ and $p = 0.9$, and all instances with 15 requests when $p = 1$. In addition, it solved one instance with 15 requests when $p = 0.9$. This behaviour may be explained by the stronger LP relaxation, as shown by column *LB0*.

Comparing Tables 2–6 and Tables 7–11 in terms of gaps, the compact formulation gives smaller values for unreliable networks: if $p = 0.2$, the average gaps when solving instances with $n = 10$ and $n = 15$ are 24.7% and 41.5%, respectively, for the compact formulation, and 40.3% and 63.0% for the non-compact formulation; if $p = 0.1$, the average gaps when solving instances with $n = 10$ and $n = 15$ are 14.5% and 27.7%, respectively, for the compact formulation, and 26.4% and 46.8% for the non-compact formulation. When p is small, the LP relaxation of the compact formulation is stronger, and the MILP solver found the optimal solution of the instances with 5 requests. Unfortunately, none of the formulations was able to solve larger instances.

Overall, the results in Tables 7–11 clearly show that the difficulty of the PPDT-SPP increases when the probability p decreases. This fact is quite remarkable, the number of instances solved for $p = 1.0, 0.9, 0.8, 0.2$, and 0.1 are 15, 12, 5, 5, and 5, respectively. Only the small instances with 5 requests could be solved for $p \leq 0.8$.

Instance	BestLB	BestUB	Gap	B&B	Time	LB0
prob5a	3400.0	3400.0	0.0	15	1.2	3057.8
prob5b	2487.1	2487.1	0.0	2	0.4	2269.7
prob5c	3657.3	3657.3	0.0	7	0.8	3181.9
prob5d	2976.8	2976.8	0.0	3	0.4	2749.1
prob5e	2989.8	2989.8	0.0	26	1.9	2492.5
avg	-	-	<i>0.0</i>	<i>10.6</i>	<i>0.9</i>	-
prob10a	3868.1	4705.0	17.8	2801	T.L.	3593.6
prob10b	3555.6	4347.0	18.2	2952	T.L.	3171.6
prob10c	3332.7	3982.0	16.3	2981	T.L.	2952.9
prob10d	3878.7	4387.0	11.6	3315	T.L.	3663.9
prob10e	4317.3	4669.0	7.5	3391	T.L.	4005.3
avg	-	-	<i>14.3</i>	<i>3088.0</i>	T.L.	-
prob15a	3960.4	4949.0	20.0	55	T.L.	3865.2
prob15b	3751.5	5016.0	25.2	42	T.L.	3509.0
prob15c	4161.5	4841.0	14.0	49	T.L.	4054.1
prob15d	4268.0	5368.0	20.5	35	T.L.	4061.0
prob15e	4159.0	5098.0	18.4	65	T.L.	3992.4
avg	-	-	<i>19.6</i>	<i>49.2</i>	T.L.	-

Table 3: Compact formulation on instances with $p = 0.9$

Instance	BestLB	BestUB	Gap	B&B	Time	LB0
prob5a	3202.6	3202.6	0.0	23	1.8	2734.3
prob5b	2403.0	2403.0	0.0	5	0.7	2054.7
prob5c	3505.5	3505.5	0.0	23	1.9	2904.9
prob5d	2810.2	2810.2	0.0	3	0.4	2447.9
prob5e	2832.5	2832.5	0.0	38	2.2	2238.4
avg	-	-	<i>0.0</i>	<i>18.4</i>	<i>1.4</i>	-
prob10a	3346.8	4495.0	25.5	2721	T.L.	3139.5
prob10b	2990.6	4178.0	28.4	2885	T.L.	2765.6
prob10c	2903.7	3873.0	25.0	2908	T.L.	2597.3
prob10d	3383.0	4205.0	19.5	2898	T.L.	3214.5
prob10e	3738.1	4450.0	16.0	3030	T.L.	3475.5
avg	-	-	<i>22.9</i>	<i>2888.4</i>	T.L.	-
prob15a	3383.3	4722.0	28.3	73	T.L.	3300.2
prob15b	3213.0	4821.0	33.4	80	T.L.	3024.4
prob15c	3608.5	4653.0	22.4	85	T.L.	3458.7
prob15d	3749.7	5138.0	27.0	51	T.L.	3496.5
prob15e	3607.7	4945.0	27.0	81	T.L.	3463.1
avg	-	-	<i>27.6</i>	<i>74.0</i>	T.L.	-

Table 4: Compact formulation on instances with $p = 0.8$

Instance	BestLB	BestUB	Gap	B&B	Time	LB0
prob5a	1398.0	1398.0	0.0	93	4.9	1198.0
prob5b	1221.8	1221.8	0.0	124	4.4	1057.1
prob5c	1520.6	1520.6	0.0	95	3.6	1301.6
prob5d	1086.6	1086.6	0.0	166	4.5	919.0
prob5e	1094.5	1094.5	0.0	143	4.8	927.4
avg	-	-	<i>0.0</i>	<i>124.2</i>	<i>4.4</i>	-
prob10a	1768.2	2384.0	25.8	2308	T.L.	1435.5
prob10b	1452.3	2001.0	27.4	2370	T.L.	1158.8
prob10c	1558.4	2092.0	25.5	2562	T.L.	1281.3
prob10d	1680.0	2181.0	23.0	2604	T.L.	1395.1
prob10e	1699.2	2170.0	21.7	2316	T.L.	1332.7
avg	-	-	<i>24.7</i>	<i>2492.0</i>	T.L.	-
prob15a	1433.7	2352.0	39.0	142	T.L.	1123.9
prob15b	1464.8	2639.0	44.5	103	T.L.	1189.1
prob15c	1448.4	2493.0	41.9	142	T.L.	1120.8
prob15d	1517.0	2522.0	39.8	169	T.L.	1168.5
prob15e	1617.0	2786.0	42.0	145	T.L.	1281.5
avg	-	-	<i>41.5</i>	<i>140.2</i>	T.L.	-

Table 5: Compact formulation on instances with $p = 0.2$

Instance	BestLB	BestUB	Gap	B&B	Time	LB0
prob5a	798.8	798.8	0.0	98	4.8	736.9
prob5b	708.6	708.6	0.0	219	5.9	656.6
prob5c	853.6	853.6	0.0	56	2.9	784.5
prob5d	592.3	592.3	0.0	102	4.1	540.7
prob5e	599.1	599.1	0.0	161	5.3	547.2
avg	-	-	0.0	127.2	4.6	-
prob10a	1261.5	1490.0	15.3	2452	T.L.	1117.4
prob10b	980.1	1166.0	15.9	2391	T.L.	844.4
prob10c	1088.2	1272.0	14.4	2610	T.L.	961.0
prob10d	1166.3	1346.0	13.3	2800	T.L.	1044.2
prob10e	1144.8	1320.0	13.3	2398	T.L.	992.9
avg	-	-	14.5	2530.2	T.L.	-
prob15a	1094.5	1484.0	26.2	176	T.L.	933.5
prob15b	1205.1	1674.0	28.0	146	T.L.	1032.4
prob15c	1124.6	1572.0	28.5	140	T.L.	942.9
prob15d	1127.6	1536.0	26.6	178	T.L.	930.7
prob15e	1227.3	1730.0	29.1	155	T.L.	1042.6
avg	-	-	27.7	159.0	T.L.	-

Table 6: Compact formulation on instances with $p = 0.1$

	BestLB	BestUB	Gap	B&B	Time	LB0	LPt	Sept	cuts	(24)	(25)	(26)	(27)	cut0
prob5a	3585.0	3585.0	0.0	3	0.1	3568.0	0.1	0.1	87	7	7	19	54	37
prob5b	2565.0	2565.0	0.0	0	0.3	2565.0	0.2	0.1	39	2	3	10	24	39
prob5c	3787.0	3787.0	0.0	0	0.3	3787.0	0.2	0.1	39	5	4	10	20	39
prob5d	3128.0	3128.0	0.0	0	0.3	3128.0	0.2	0.0	22	3	6	1	12	22
prob5e	3123.0	3123.0	0.0	3	0.1	3061.2	0.1	0.0	69	12	14	18	25	53
avg	-	-	0.0	1.2	0.2	-	0.1	0.1	51.2	5.8	6.8	11.6	27.0	38.0
prob10a	4896.0	4896.0	0.0	39	8.4	4522.1	2.1	6.3	595	84	56	112	343	126
prob10b	4490.0	4490.0	0.0	60	14.3	4019.8	4.2	10.0	794	78	113	137	466	74
prob10c	4070.0	4070.0	0.0	3	0.3	4054.5	0.1	0.2	222	30	40	43	109	104
prob10d	4551.0	4551.0	0.0	4	0.9	4459.0	0.3	0.6	210	14	30	34	132	100
prob10e	4874.0	4874.0	0.0	8	1.4	4770.8	0.5	0.9	530	113	45	69	303	164
avg	-	-	0.0	22.8	5.1	-	1.5	3.6	470.2	63.8	56.8	79.0	270.6	113.6
prob15a	5150.0	5150.0	0.0	155	158.3	4789.5	83.0	75.3	2504	266	289	412	1537	306
prob15b	5391.0	5391.0	0.0	884	1305.0	4763.9	884.6	420.4	5958	564	490	914	3990	324
prob15c	5008.0	5008.0	0.0	5	2.6	4917.4	0.8	1.8	545	111	68	97	269	193
prob15d	5566.0	5566.0	0.0	274	305.7	5074.3	173.4	132.2	2940	330	353	452	1805	303
prob15e	5229.0	5229.0	0.0	9	6.1	5117.1	1.6	4.4	601	68	65	77	391	237
avg	-	-	0.0	265.4	355.5	-	228.7	126.8	2509.6	267.8	253.0	390.4	1598.4	272.6

Table 7: Non-compact formulation on instances with $p = 1$

	BestLB	BestUB	Gap	B&B	Time	LB0	LPt	Sept	cuts	(24)	(25)	(26)	(27)	cut0
prob5a	3400.0	3400.0	0.0	32	1.6	3184.0	0.2	1.4	215	15	17	24	159	54
prob5b	2487.1	2487.1	0.0	10	0.6	2386.6	0.2	0.4	89	6	8	15	60	49
prob5c	3657.3	3657.3	0.0	17	0.8	3424.8	0.2	0.6	119	10	11	18	80	60
prob5d	2976.8	2976.8	0.0	14	0.8	2806.0	0.2	0.6	98	9	14	7	68	38
prob5e	2989.8	2989.8	0.0	33	1.4	2667.6	0.3	1.1	201	21	32	35	113	50
avg	-	-	0.0	21.2	1.1	-	0.2	0.8	144.4	12.2	16.4	19.8	96.0	50.2
prob10a	4704.2	4704.2	0.0	1724	634.4	3830.2	403.5	230.9	4758	377	285	596	3500	118
prob10b	4346.0	4346.0	0.0	2713	1014.1	3374.4	669.2	344.9	5971	459	535	658	4319	81
prob10c	3981.0	3981.0	0.0	279	72.3	3419.9	26.2	46.1	1615	84	111	135	1285	104
prob10d	4384.4	4384.4	0.0	638	185.0	3815.4	93.0	92.0	2682	175	157	236	2114	108
prob10e	4668.7	4668.7	0.0	398	106.3	4012.8	49.7	56.7	1940	207	195	276	1262	97
avg	-	-	0.0	1150.4	402.4	-	248.3	154.1	3393.2	260.4	256.6	380.2	2496.0	101.6
prob15a	4721.7	4949.0	4.6	4084	T.L.	4024.0	5538.1	1662.8	7581	593	563	678	5747	248
prob15b	4755.2	5016.0	5.2	3830	T.L.	3979.7	5598.9	1602.1	7519	501	577	779	5662	272
prob15c	4840.1	4840.1	0.0	1850	1646.9	4112.4	940.9	706.0	5013	484	419	371	3739	220
prob15d	4979.3	5368.0	7.2	3619	T.L.	4226.1	5646.3	1554.7	7895	912	711	861	5411	250
prob15e	5098.0	5098.0	0.0	5249	6709.9	4300.5	4835.7	1874.3	8999	657	699	728	6915	257
avg	-	-	3.4	3726.4	5992.0	-	4512.0	1480.0	7401.4	629.4	593.8	683.4	5494.8	249.4

Table 8: Non-compact formulation on instances with $p = 0.9$

	BestLB	BestUB	Gap	B&B	Time	LB0	LPt	Sept	cuts	(24)	(25)	(26)	(27)	cut0
prob5a	3202.6	3202.6	0.0	103	4.4	2797.9	0.8	3.6	413	30	35	51	297	49
prob5b	2403.0	2403.0	0.0	37	1.7	2115.1	0.3	1.4	201	14	20	20	147	41
prob5c	3505.5	3505.5	0.0	64	2.7	2972.6	0.4	2.3	316	26	14	34	242	51
prob5d	2810.2	2810.2	0.0	72	2.9	2430.6	0.5	2.5	295	28	28	29	210	39
prob5e	2832.5	2832.5	0.0	146	6.0	2296.1	1.3	4.7	586	57	57	87	385	45
avg	-	-	0.0	84.4	3.6	-	0.7	2.9	362.2	31.0	30.8	44.2	256.2	45.0
prob10a	4177.7	4495.0	7.1	6834	T.L.	3196.7	6271.6	928.8	9656	766	620	1221	7049	135
prob10b	3768.3	4178.0	9.8	6993	T.L.	2809.7	6248.1	952.2	9276	772	788	904	6812	139
prob10c	3713.6	3873.0	4.1	6765	T.L.	2844.1	6243.0	957.3	8887	393	435	576	7483	125
prob10d	4003.9	4205.0	4.8	6738	T.L.	3209.3	6275.2	925.2	9663	625	558	792	7688	93
prob10e	4266.3	4450.0	4.1	6896	T.L.	3395.1	6281.8	918.6	8768	859	715	957	6237	117
avg	-	-	6.0	6845.2	T.L.	-	6264.0	936.4	9250.0	683.0	623.2	890.0	7053.8	121.8
prob15a	3986.8	4722.0	15.6	5017	T.L.	3278.7	5192.5	2008.3	6859	583	577	689	5010	195
prob15b	4002.9	4821.0	17.0	4290	T.L.	3245.9	5421.5	1779.3	7687	519	633	713	5822	238
prob15c	4134.1	4653.0	11.2	5167	T.L.	3342.3	5142.7	2058.0	7773	739	643	508	5883	212
prob15d	4206.5	5138.0	18.1	4196	T.L.	3429.7	5472.1	1728.9	7905	972	711	959	5263	253
prob15e	4273.8	4945.0	13.6	4538	T.L.	3504.8	5354.3	1846.4	8118	730	706	771	5911	202
avg	-	-	15.1	4641.6	T.L.	-	5316.6	1884.2	7668.4	708.6	654.0	728.0	5577.8	220.0

Table 9: Non-compact formulation on instances with $p = 0.8$

	BestLB	BestUB	Gap	B&B	Time	LB0	LPt	Sept	cuts	(24)	(25)	(26)	(27)	cut0
prob5a	1398.0	1398.0	0.0	6087	515.6	1179.9	341.5	174.1	4475	309	277	449	3440	52
prob5b	1221.8	1221.8	0.0	3722	258.6	1023.5	145.8	112.8	3514	310	211	348	2645	43
prob5c	1520.6	1520.6	0.0	10451	1034.1	1243.7	713.4	320.7	5580	329	237	420	4594	41
prob5d	1086.6	1086.6	0.0	15932	1571.9	872.7	1142.4	429.5	6597	310	286	609	5392	36
prob5e	1094.5	1094.5	0.0	15341	1664.6	872.3	1226.3	438.3	6682	325	305	525	5527	47
avg	-	-	0.0	10306.6	1009.0	-	713.9	295.1	5369.6	316.6	263.2	470.2	4319.6	43.8
prob10a	1468.9	2384.0	38.4	3377	T.L.	1269.8	6671.5	528.9	14651	2135	1116	3148	8252	145
prob10b	1060.3	2001.0	47.0	4272	T.L.	940.9	6563.6	636.8	12142	1586	1476	2095	6985	102
prob10c	1213.9	2092.0	42.0	5303	T.L.	1077.8	6437.6	762.9	12364	1404	1008	1933	8019	128
prob10d	1412.8	2181.0	35.2	3999	T.L.	1228.5	6607.0	593.4	12485	1624	1083	2624	7154	154
prob10e	1320.5	2170.0	39.1	4175	T.L.	1153.3	6498.2	702.1	13692	2315	1266	2297	7814	99
avg	-	-	40.3	4225.2	T.L.	-	6555.6	644.8	13066.8	1812.8	1189.8	2419.4	7644.8	125.6
prob15a	923.2	2352.0	60.7	3056	T.L.	824.5	5745.1	1455.8	11381	1350	1028	1698	7305	183
prob15b	977.0	2639.0	63.0	2194	T.L.	873.7	5976.1	1224.9	12665	1498	1154	1745	8268	245
prob15c	897.5	2493.0	64.0	2989	T.L.	794.7	5680.4	1520.7	13173	1517	942	1349	9365	162
prob15d	900.6	2522.0	64.3	2262	T.L.	814.2	6005.6	1196.0	12947	1950	1101	2299	7597	257
prob15e	1026.1	2786.0	63.2	2490	T.L.	924.0	5946.4	1254.8	12168	1513	1317	1936	7402	205
avg	-	-	63.0	2598.2	T.L.	-	5870.7	1330.4	12466.8	1565.6	1108.4	1805.4	7987.4	210.4

Table 10: Non-compact formulation on instances with $p = 0.2$

	BestLB	BestUB	Gap	B&B	Time	LB0	LPt	Sept	cuts	(24)	(25)	(26)	(27)	cut0
prob5a	798.8	798.8	0.0	8372	843.6	731.4	546.6	297.0	5159	305	250	433	4171	70
prob5b	708.6	708.6	0.0	6254	550.9	646.5	326.4	224.4	4525	329	265	410	3521	33
prob5c	853.6	853.6	0.0	16562	1993.1	767.7	1374.1	619.0	6587	317	265	469	5536	51
prob5d	592.3	592.3	0.0	21388	2543.0	526.3	1822.7	720.4	7380	329	277	614	6160	35
prob5e	599.1	599.1	0.0	21917	2818.2	530.4	2070.3	747.9	7511	309	322	620	6260	47
avg	-	-	0.0	14898.6	1749.7	-	1228.0	521.7	6232.4	317.8	275.8	509.2	5129.6	47.2
prob10a	1104.8	1490.0	25.8	3371	T.L.	1056.4	6567.8	632.7	17888	1983	1468	2281	12156	184
prob10b	806.4	1166.0	30.8	3173	T.L.	763.0	6625.7	574.6	14756	2139	1269	3167	8181	113
prob10c	928.4	1272.0	27.0	4430	T.L.	881.3	6440.1	760.4	13163	1713	1066	2322	8062	98
prob10d	1042.9	1346.0	22.5	3505	T.L.	979.6	6566.5	634.0	14165	1787	1328	2891	8159	152
prob10e	982.0	1320.0	25.6	3166	T.L.	925.2	6636.9	563.5	16212	2550	1719	2632	9311	130
avg	-	-	26.4	3529.0	T.L.	-	6567.4	633.0	15236.8	2034.4	1370.0	2658.6	9173.8	135.4
prob15a	820.9	1484.0	44.7	2077	T.L.	790.9	6004.4	1196.4	15238	1598	1256	1714	10670	208
prob15b	915.2	1674.0	45.3	1508	T.L.	881.8	6261.8	939.3	15970	2025	1399	2559	9987	228
prob15c	824.9	1572.0	47.5	1690	T.L.	791.3	6146.8	1054.4	19371	2237	1517	1850	13767	166
prob15d	792.2	1536.0	48.4	1876	T.L.	768.0	6140.8	1060.1	14566	2113	1502	2442	8509	275
prob15e	901.7	1730.0	47.9	1825	T.L.	874.9	6133.4	1067.8	16091	1752	1725	1917	10697	184
avg	-	-	46.8	1795.2	T.L.	-	6137.4	1063.6	16247.2	1945.0	1479.8	2096.4	10726.0	212.2

Table 11: Non-compact formulation on instances with $p = 0.1$

Focusing on the columns from *LPt* to *cut0*, Tables 7–11 show that the time consumed by the separation procedures is often smaller than half of the time consumed by the MILP solver. For instance, if $n = 15$, the time consumed by the MILP solver is 229, 4512, 5317, 5871 and 6137 seconds for $p = 1, 0.9, 0.8, 0.2$ and 0.1 , respectively, while the time required by the separation procedures is 127, 1480, 1884, 1330, and 1064. The computational time for separating is larger than the time consumed by the MILP solver only for very small problems ($n = 5$) and on reliable networks ($p = 0.9, 0.8$). Moreover, all the inequalities (24), (25), (26) and (27) are helpful in the branch-and-cut procedure: although column (26) always has greater values than columns (24), (25) and (27), none of them is negligible. Finally, comparing *cuts* with *cut0* it can be observed that the number of cuts separated at the root node is by far smaller than the total number of cuts separated over the whole branch-and-cut algorithm.

The two implemented codes solved all the small instances (5 requests), but the one based on the compact formulation ran faster, specially when p was small. In fact, the average computing time in Tables 5 and 6 is 4.5 seconds, while the average computing time in Tables 10 and 11 is 1379.4 seconds. On the larger instances (10 and 15 requests), only the code based on the non-compact formulation was able to find some optimal solutions (when p was large). The lower bounds provided by the non-compact formulation were better on the instances with 15 request and $p = 1$. None of the two formulations improved the initial heuristic solution (the PDTSP solution) when the time limit was reached.

Table 12 shows the length of the optimal a priori routes found by the non-compact formulation for the instances with 5 requests, which are the only ones that could be optimally solved for all values of p . Thus, this set of instances is used to study the differences between the optimal solutions of the PDTSP and the ones of the PPDTSP. Note that the PPDTSP for $p = 1$ is in fact the PDTSP, so this length coincides with the expected cost of the a posteriori route, and is the optimal PDTSP value. For p equal to 0.9 and 0.8, the length of the optimal PPDTSP is the same than for $p = 1$. This holds because the optimal PPDTSP is the same that the optimal PDTSP route. Thus, using the optimal PDTSP as a heuristic solution for the PPDTSP provided in fact the optimal solutions in these cases. For p equal to 0.2 and 0.1, the length of the optimal a priori route increases, which shows that the optimal PPDTSP routes differ from the optimal PDTSP routes, as observed in Section 4. Nevertheless, although not shown in this table, it is important to mention that the average gap between the optimal PPDTSP cost and the expected cost of the heuristic solution provided by the optimal PDTSP was 0.66% and 0.50% for $p = 0.2$ and $p = 0.1$, respectively. So, even when p is small, the heuristic solution is quite good, at least for instances with 5 requests.

From the computational results it follows that instances with $p = 0.1, 0.2$ are more difficult than instances with $p = 0.8, 0.9$. This is partially due to the coefficients in the objective function (obtained from the travel costs and the probability p).

For any (i, j) , when $p = 0.1, 0.2$ the coefficients of $x_{ij}^1, \dots, x_{ij}^{n-1}$ are large fractions of the coefficient of x_{ij}^0 , while when $p = 0.8, 0.9$ those are very small fractions of the coefficient of x_{ij}^0 . Thus, problems with $p = 0.1, 0.2$ afford much more relevant scenarios than problems with $p = 0.8, 0.9$.

	$p = 1$	$p = 0.9$	$p = 0.8$	$p = 0.2$	$p = 0.1$
prob5a	3585	3585	3585	3840	3840
prob5b	2565	2565	2565	2662	2662
prob5c	3787	3787	3787	3851	3851
prob5d	3128	3128	3128	3230	3230
prob5e	3123	3123	3123	3267	3841

Table 12: Length of the optimal PPDTSP solutions for instances with 5 requests

7 Conclusions

This paper proposes and compares two mathematical formulations for finding optimal solutions for the Probabilistic Pickup-and-Delivery Travelling Salesman Problem. The problem addresses the service of a set of n potential requests. The realization of each request follows a Bernoulli probability distribution with parameter p . The problem looks for an a priori route to pickup and deliver all requests, but then a single vehicle following that a priori route will only serve the requests made, thus leading to an a posteriori route. The aim is to minimize the expected cost of the a posteriori route. This problem was already introduced in the literature by other authors, but it was addressed only from a heuristic point of view.

The two formulations are based on $O(n^3)$ binary variables. One model has the advantage of containing a polynomial number of constraints, while the other model is based on an exponential number of inequalities. Computational results showed no dominance of one formulation with respect to the other, although some instances with 15 requests were solved by the non-compact formulation only.

The paper also discusses the quality of using optimal solutions of the problem with $p = 1$ as feasible solutions for the problem with $p < 1$. Although this heuristic solution could be optimal when p is large, its performance may not be so good when p is small.

An interesting topic for future research is the case in which the network has requests with $p = 1$ and requests with $p < 1$. The extension of the PPDTSP in which a location may be pickup and/or delivery of several requests is also of interest. Another challenging related problem would be the problem with incomplete information, i.e., the problem of determining the route with minimum total expected cost when the vehicle does not have advance information about whether a given request is going to be formalized or not, and thus it must visit all the pickup nodes.

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Author contributions

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